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2030 Roadmap for Improving Institutional Research Cultures to Strengthen Research Ethics and Integrity in Europe

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Executive Summary

Research misconduct (RM) — defined as fabrication, falsification, and plagiarism, along with other unacceptable research practices — and contestable research practices (CRPs) — research behaviours that are not universally proscribed, but can be unethical in certain contexts — undermine scientific credibility, distort knowledge production, damage careers, and erode public trust. These harms are often exacerbated by systemic pressures, inequitable structures, the politicisation of science and scholarship, and evolving technologies such as generative AI introduce new integrity risks.

This Roadmap sets out a comprehensive, system-wide strategy to improve the Research Ethics and Integrity (RE/RI) environment and reduce RM by 2030. It draws its recommendations from the evidence-based findings of the Horizon Europe [BEYOND project](#), which adopts an ecosystemic approach that examines the relationship between institutional and individual factors that contribute to RM, rather than solely focussing on individual ‘bad apples’ as their cause. It also builds on established European and international guidance, including the [ENRIO Recommendations for the Investigation of Research Misconduct](#) (2020) and the [ENRIO Handbook on Whistleblower Protection in Research](#) (2023).

The Roadmap is structured across four strategic pillars:

- I. Research Governance Reform** – Strengthening reporting, investigation,

adjudication, publishing transparency, research rehabilitation, and RE/RI monitoring systems.

- II. Research Culture Transformation** – Fostering good research practices, career-stage support, incentives for integrity, and behavioural nudges to support responsible conduct of research.
- III. Evolving RE/RI Education and Research** – Improving training design, evaluation, and evidence-based policymaking.
- IV. Enhancing Public Trust and Societal Impact** – Enhancing transparency, communication, and trust-building with diverse publics.

The strategy unfolds across three time horizons:

- By 2027 (establishment and early implementation):** Establish secure whistleblowing systems, fair adjudication processes, transparent publishing mechanisms, and foundational cultural reforms.
- By 2028 (institutional embedding and scaling):** Develop inclusive and contextualized RE/RI frameworks, implement joined-up monitoring systems, embed incentives, and evaluate the effectiveness of RE/RI interventions.
- By 2030 (maturity and consolidation):** Institutionalize learning cultures, align incentives with integrity, and embed sustainable oversight mechanisms.

By 2030, institutions can reduce the prevalence of RM and CRPs, improve investigation processes, increase training effectiveness, enhance reporting mechanisms and whistleblower protection, and strengthen public trust in science and academic scholarship.

List of Acronyms

KPI	Key Performance Indicator
RE/RI	Research Ethics and Integrity
REC	Research Ethics Committee
RFO	Research Funding Organisation
RIO	Research Integrity Office
RM	Research Misconduct
RPO	Research Performing Organisation

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1. Introduction

1.1. Purpose

Research misconduct (RM) presents a persistent and evolving risk to the integrity of science and academic scholarship. While fabrication, falsification, and plagiarism remain relatively rare, other unacceptable research practices — including selective reporting, inappropriate authorship, poor data management, and the misuse of AI tools — are becoming more widespread. Alongside these sit contestable research practices (CRPs): behaviours whose ethical acceptability is not universally agreed upon and depends on context, including the academic discipline and the methods used to produce knowledge. While not inherently unethical, CRPs can raise research integrity concerns when used inappropriately. For example, forming a hypothesis after seeing the results (known as HARKing) is generally considered problematic in quantitative research, but working inductively from data is standard practice in qualitative research. Taken together, these practices can undermine scientific credibility, distort knowledge production, harm careers, and erode public trust in science and scholarship.

The causes of RM and CRPs are multifactorial: perverse incentives, career insecurity, hyper-competition, inadequate mentoring and training, unclear standards, the politicisation of research and weak enforcement mechanisms. Identity-based exclusion and power imbalances further compound vulnerability, particularly for early-

career researchers, and [researchers from underrepresented and marginalised groups](#).

This Roadmap adopts a systemic perspective to provide a programme of recommendations to reduce the frequency and impacts of RMs and CRPs on the research environment in Europe. It recognises that reducing RM requires more than punitive measures; it demands cultural transformation, supportive infrastructures, transparent governance and continuous institutional learning. Meaningful change also requires coordination between the constituent members of the ecosystem including: Research Performing Organisations (RPOs), Research Ethics Committees (RECs); Research Funding Organisations (RFOs); national Research Integrity Offices (RIOs); other Research Ethics and Integrity bodies such as EUREC, ENRIO, ALLEA; policymakers; research ethics and integrity educators; and individual researchers across all disciplines and career stages.

1.2. Roadmap implementation

The Roadmap is intended as a high-level strategic framework that sets a clear direction while remaining flexible enough to accommodate the diverse nature of the European research environment. Rather than prescribing uniform, step-by-step actions, it provides guiding principles and priorities that can be interpreted and applied appropriately within specific national and institutional contexts. This approach recognises that conditions, capacities, and challenges vary widely, and that effective solutions should be tailored accordingly. As a result, the Roadmap

serves as a reference point for alignment and coordination, enabling stakeholders to develop means of implementation that are relevant, pragmatic and actionable.

Whilst the Roadmap provides strategic guidance on desirable measures to improve research culture, further work is required by stakeholders to clarify how they will cooperate at local and national levels, and how Key Performance Indicators (KPIs) for evaluation of successful progress towards objectives will be defined and measured.

The Roadmap signposts where additional work is required to develop suitable measurements and define appropriate KPIs. Furthermore, many of the recommendations in the Roadmap will require moderate to significant financial and human resources to implement. Additional work is required by stakeholders to scope institutional readiness, and risks and barriers along with appropriate mitigations. Stakeholders will also need to calculate the resources required to implement these recommendations in relation to their local, regional and domain-specific contexts, and to identify from where resources will be allocated. Policymakers can play a significant role here in supporting capacity building and resource allocation.

1.3. Context of the BEYOND project

The Roadmap synthesises the results of the Horizon Europe BEYOND Project. BEYOND has worked to promote adherence to Research Ethics and Integrity (RE/RI) standards and best practice to prevent and mitigate RM by developing and communicating systemic interventions that address the complex interrelation between individual and institutional responsibilities that contribute to ethically responsible and scientifically rigorous

research environments. It has done so through a four-phase approach:

1. EXPLORE the existing literature on behavioural ethics and moral psychology as well as the socio-economic consequences of RM.
2. ENGAGE involved stakeholders in a public consultation.
3. GUIDE and
4. EQUIP stakeholders in the research ecosystem.

For the GUIDE and EQUIP phases the project has produced and tested environmental interventions (i.e. nudges) informed by behavioural psychology to promote RE/RI and prevent RM, methodologies for measuring the effectiveness of RE/RI training on the attitudes and behaviours of students and researchers, as well as guidelines and a best practice manual to support stakeholders with recommendations to improve their practices and protocols (see Annex A: Further Reading).

This Roadmap forms the final part of this phase, by providing a structured and time-bound programme of aligned intervention to facilitate improvements in RE/RI culture by 2030. The roadmap consolidates recommendations developed from results obtained across the project including the [literature review on behavioural ethics and moral psychology and review of recent case studies](#), [public consultation on RE/RI culture](#), the [BEYOND Guidelines for Preventing and Addressing Research Misconduct](#) and the BEYOND Best Practices Manual: A Complement to the BEYOND Guidelines for Preventing and Addressing Research Misconduct.¹ A draft of the Roadmap was validated by the

¹ The BEYOND Best Practices Manual will be available on the [publications page](#) of the project website from late June 2026.

BEYOND Stakeholder Advisory Board and project contributors, incorporating their feedback to refine the recommendations, improve accessibility, and ensure the Roadmap’s alignment with user needs (see Annex B for a more detailed description of the methodology).

1.4. Vision and Guiding Principles

In line with the systemic perspective advanced by the BEYOND Project, research stakeholders are encouraged to adopt approaches to conducting research that recognise research

integrity not only as an individual commitment, but as a shared endeavour across RPOs, RFOs, publishers, policymakers, and researchers. This perspective highlights the value of collectively fostering practices grounded in fairness, inclusivity, transparency, and accountability.

In practice, this can involve supporting research adjudication processes that prioritise fairness, due process, and proportionality in addressing integrity-related concerns, while taking care to safeguard both whistleblowers and respondents from harm, retaliation, or unjust treatment.

Vision & Guiding Principles

Institutions may also seek to reflect inclusivity and disciplinary diversity within RE/RI frameworks, applying integrity principles in ways that are consistent yet sensitive to different research contexts. Similarly, research practices and RE/RI processes—including reporting, whistleblowing, and adjudication—can benefit from attentiveness to uneven power dynamics among researchers, including those related to seniority, gender, as well as pay, working conditions, and job precarity.

Furthermore, incentive structures ought to be realigned to reward responsible research practices rather than purely quantitative outputs. Cases of RM should be treated not only as matters of accountability but also as opportunities for institutional learning and cultural reform. Public trust can be fostered through transparent and accountable governance supported by independent oversight mechanisms. Core principles underpinning this vision include shared responsibility; fairness and proportionality; transparency balanced with confidentiality; evidence-informed policymaking; inclusivity and contextual sensitivity; continuous learning; rehabilitation and restorative justice where appropriate; and independence and accountability in investigation and adjudication. Together these principles illustrate a whole-system commitment to strengthening research integrity as a resilient adaptive and socially responsible ecosystem by 2030.

1.5. Roadmap structure and timeline

The Roadmap is organised around four interlinked strategic pillars that collectively guide the advancement of research excellence and

integrity. **Pillar I: Research Governance Reform** focuses on strengthening reporting, investigation, adjudication, and publishing transparency, alongside research rehabilitation and the development of robust RE/RI monitoring systems.

Pillar II: Research Culture Transformation aims to foster good research practices by providing tailored career-stage support, offering incentives for integrity, and introducing behavioural nudges to encourage the responsible conduct of research.

Pillar III: Evolving RE/RI Education and Research prioritises the improvement of training design, evidence-based policymaking, and the evaluation of research integrity interventions. **Pillar IV:**

Enhancing Public Trust and Societal Impact

emphasises communication and trust-building with diverse audiences to ensure public trust in scientific research and scholarship, as well as the institutions that comprise the European research environment, and that research engages and benefits society.

The four pillars are implemented across three time-horizons: **By 2027** focuses on **establishment and early implementation** focussing on whistleblowing and reporting processes, adjudication, publishing and cultural reforms; **by 2028** the focus shifts to **institutional embedding and scaling** of inclusive frameworks, integrated monitoring, incentives and assessment of interventions. **By 2030** a clear programme of change should be in a phase of **maturity and consolidation** that institutionalises learning cultures, aligns incentives with integrity, and establishes enduring oversight mechanisms. Together, this structured approach enables a gradual and sustainable transformation of the European research environment to embed integrity and ethical conduct at the heart of institutional research cultures.

POLICY ROADMAP

Research Ethics & Integrity Roadmap 2030

● Research Governance Reform ● Research Culture Transformation ● Enhancing Public Trust & Societal Impact ● Evolving RE/RI Education & Research

Implementation Timeline (2026–2030)

Phase	Focus
2026–2027	Whistleblowing systems, adjudication reform, publishing transparency, cultural groundwork
2027–2028	Monitoring systems, inclusive frameworks, incentive reform, improved training
2028–2030	Institutionalised learning culture, sustainable oversight

2. Pillar I: Research Governance Reform

2.1. Improving transparency and fairness in academic publishing

Timescale: 2026–2028 **Stakeholders involved:** academic publishers, RPOs, RFOs

OBJECTIVE	ACTIONS TO ACHIEVE OBJECTIVE
<p>Peer Review</p> <p>Increase transparency and fairness in peer review processes</p>	<p>By 2028</p> <p>Academic publishers should implement measures to support transparent peer review. These include:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • clear communication of peer review processes; • reviewer guidelines published on journal websites; and • supportive mechanisms for conflict resolution. <p>By 2030</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • RPOs and RFOs should encourage and support researchers to publish exclusively in venues that adhere to transparent editorial standards.
<p>Editorial Investigations</p> <p>Improve transparency and efficiency in undertaking and reporting editorial investigations and retraction processes</p>	<p>By 2028</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Publishers should establish clear timelines and performance targets for resolution of editorial investigations and retraction processes.

Unreliable Research

Prevent prolonged circulation of unreliable findings

By 2028

Publishers should:

- expedite investigation and retraction processes; and
- clearly display expressions of concern if an article under review is being investigated, accompanied by a clear timeline for resolution.

2.2. Improving RE/RI definitions and frameworks

Timescale: 2028 - 2030 **Stakeholders involved:** RPOs, RFOs, RE/RI bodies, RIOs and researchers

OBJECTIVE	ACTIONS TO ACHIEVE OBJECTIVE
<p>Context Awareness</p> <p>Embed contextually sensitive interpretation of CRPs that acknowledge how various academic disciplines understand knowledge differently</p>	<p>By 2030</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • RE/RI procedures and frameworks should be developed collaboratively with the research community to ensure the development of shared standards that can fairly and feasibly be applied across all disciplines. • RE/RI bodies and RIOs could consider whether a CRP is harmful or problematic in a particular case or situation, e.g., HARKing (modifying a hypothesis after gathering data to better fit the evidence).
<p>Diversity and Inclusion</p> <p>Institutional, national, and regional RE/RI frameworks should reflect linguistic, cultural and geographical pluralism, and address identity and gender-based inclusion</p>	<p>By 2030</p> <p>RPOs, RFOs and RE/RI bodies should ensure that RE/RI frameworks are inclusive, accessible and context-sensitive by:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • translating guidelines into multiple languages; and • developing multilingual glossaries and training modules.

Emerging Technologies

Update RE/RI definitions, frameworks and monitoring to address emerging technologies including the use of generative artificial intelligence (AI)

By 2030

- RPOs and RFOs should update RE/RI definitions, frameworks and policies to reflect evolving research methods and new technologies, including generative AI. This should incorporate the European Commission’s [Living Guidelines on the Responsible Use of Generative AI in Research](#).
- Researchers should ensure awareness and implementation of guidance on the use of novel technologies like generative AI, including compliance with legal requirements and ethical best practices concerning data privacy, confidentiality and intellectual property rights.

2.3. Ensuring reliable and trustworthy reporting and whistleblowing mechanisms

Timescale: 2026 - 2028 **Stakeholders involved:** RPOs, RFOs, RE/RI bodies and RIOs, policymakers

OBJECTIVE	ACTIONS TO ACHIEVE OBJECTIVE
<p>Reporting Mechanisms</p> <p>Establish accessible, confidential, and secure mechanisms for reporting RM concerns that prioritise fairness and non-retaliation</p>	<p>By 2027</p> <p>RPOs, RE/RI bodies and RIOs should:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • establish secure and trustworthy channels for reporting concerns about RM, such as encrypted online platforms or designated integrity officers; • provide clear information on the reporting process, including what individuals can expect in terms of confidentiality and whistleblower protections, investigation processes, timelines, and outcomes; • provide targeted assurances and support to early-career researchers and those in vulnerable positions to reduce the risk of coercion, institutional pressure, or abuse of power; and • ensure that respondents to allegations are not automatically subject to suspicion or sanctions before investigations conclude, in compliance with national legislation.

Whistleblower Protection

Create and enforce clear, consistent, and comprehensive whistleblower protection guidelines that meet recognised international standards, especially for early-career and vulnerable researchers, to prevent retaliation

By 2028

RPOs should:

- coordinate between human resources departments, research offices and institutional ombudspersons to operationalise whistleblower protection frameworks; and
- roll-out training sessions for integrity officers and investigative committees to reinforce principles of fairness, non-retaliation, and procedural transparency.

Supportive Environment

Foster a supportive institutional environment, including informal channels for advice and mentoring, to encourage responsible reporting without fear of reprisal

By 2028

RPOs should:

- implement communication strategies, including induction briefings and internal guidance materials to normalise the use of reporting mechanisms and enhance trust among the research community; and
- provide informal advisory channels for ombudspersons or trusted mentors so researchers can discreetly seek confidential advice prior to formal reporting.

By 2030

Policymakers should support by:

- defining and enforcing national and European-level whistleblower protection guidelines, ensuring consistent legal safeguards across institutions. Sources for best practice include the [ENRIO Handbook on Whistleblower Protection in Research](#) and the guidelines set out in the [ISO 37002:2021 standard on Whistleblowing Management Systems](#), which emphasises a systems-oriented approach.
- conducting ongoing reviews and stakeholder consultations to ensure reporting mechanisms remain credible, effective, and aligned with evolving legal and ethical standards.

2.4. Ensuring fair and transparent RE/RI adjudication processes

Timescale: 2026 - 2028 **Stakeholders involved:** RPOs, RFOs, RE/RI bodies and RIOs, academic publishers, policymakers

OBJECTIVE	ACTIONS TO ACHIEVE OBJECTIVE
<p>Investigation Processes</p> <p>Promote fairness, consistency, and transparency in RM adjudication</p>	<p>By 2028</p> <p>RPOs, RFOs and RE/RI bodies should:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • adopt the ENRIO Recommendations for the Investigation of Research Misconduct to ensure allegations of misconduct are handled with shared standards, fair procedures, and consistent investigation processes. • implement procedures to identify potential misuse of misconduct allegations and prevent abuse of investigation processes. Clearly define RM and distinguish it from academic disagreements. • develop and enforce clear, pragmatic timelines for RM investigations to minimise the circulation of fraudulent data and protect the integrity of academic research.
<p>Independent Oversight</p> <p>Establish independent oversight mechanisms to uphold individual and institutional accountability</p>	<p>By 2030</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • RFOs, RPOs, RE/RI bodies and RIOs, publishers and policymakers, should work together to establish independent oversight committees to prevent internal cover-ups and ensure accountability. These committees should be trained to operate effectively in politically sensitive contexts and act freely and independently from institutional or political influence.
<p>Support for Participants</p> <p>Ensure appropriate support for whistleblowers, respondents, witnesses, and case handlers throughout research adjudication processes</p>	<p>By 2030</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • RPOs should provide comprehensive support for all individuals involved in RM proceedings by offering psychological counselling, legal advice, and access to independent advisory services.

2.5. Take steps to facilitate rehabilitation and reintegration

Timescale: 2026 - 2028 **Stakeholders involved:** RPOs, RE/RI bodies and RIOs

OBJECTIVE	ACTIONS TO ACHIEVE OBJECTIVE
<p>Reintegration</p> <p>Provide structured pathways for reintegrating researchers following misconduct investigations</p>	<p>By 2028</p> <p>RPOs can support reintegration by:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • providing access to retraining or re-certification in good research practices, alongside regular progress reviews and psychosocial support where needed; • agreeing reintegration plans with implicated researchers which may include reassignment to less sensitive research tasks, mandatory ethics training, and participation in supervised research projects; and • establishing mentorship programmes pairing reintegrating researchers with colleagues who have undertaken integrity training.
<p>Exoneration</p> <p>Ensure exonerated researchers regain professional standing and well-being</p>	<p>By 2028</p> <p>RPOs can:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • issue public statements of exoneration and assist with re-engagement in research teams; and • provide formal acknowledgements of personal and professional distress caused by the investigation processes and engage with researchers to remediate harm.
<p>Team recovery</p> <p>Support affected teams and institutions in restoring trust with stakeholders and mitigating long-term reputational impacts</p>	<p>By 2028</p> <p>Where entire teams or departments are affected, RPOs can:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • provide collective recovery initiatives including group counselling, reflective workshops, and targeted leadership support; and • conduct restorative justice approaches in cases where misconduct has affected collaborators or institutional trust.

Frameworks

Develop consistent frameworks balancing accountability, fairness, and professional redemption

By 2030

- RPOs can implement standardised frameworks for rehabilitation processes balancing transparency and confidentiality, ensuring processes are fair and proportionate.
- RE/RI bodies could advise RPOs in designing frameworks for reintegrating researchers who have committed RM.

2.6. Joined-up monitoring and evaluation of RM

Timescale: 2028 - 2030 **Stakeholders involved:** RPOs, RE/RI bodies and RIOs

OBJECTIVE	ACTION
<p>Monitoring systems</p> <p>Establish robust and transparent monitoring and evaluation systems across institutions and national levels</p>	<p>By 2030</p> <p>RE/RI bodies and RIOs should:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • collaborate with RPOs to identify existing monitoring systems and measurements already in place that can be scaled-up and shared; • evaluate the feasibility and effective design of longitudinal, institutional, and national-level surveys to track the prevalence and patterns of misconduct; • design and implement an interoperable rubric for reporting, monitoring, and analysing misconduct case studies, incorporating criteria that support qualitative depth; and • conduct independent audits of REI policies and oversight structures to support compliance with best practices.

Institutional learning

Promote data-driven institutional learning to strengthen ethical research cultures

By 2030

- RPOs should collect and analyse data from investigations and outcomes to strengthen research culture, with institutional reputation never overriding commitment to honesty and integrity.
- National RE/RI bodies and RIOs should conduct periodic post-case reviews to identify gaps in policy, weaknesses in oversight, and systemic factors contributing to misconduct, and embed lessons into policy updates and training initiatives.
- Data gathered on misconduct cases by National RE/RI bodies, RIOs and RPOs should be made accessible to RE/RI researchers, civil society, journalists, and the public in a way that preserves privacy and confidentiality.

International collaboration

Enhance international collaboration and information-sharing for effective oversight

By 2030

- RPO leaders and RIOs should work with national RE/RI bodies to establish mechanisms for better information-sharing and reporting on misconduct at both national and international levels. This includes identifying individuals who have committed serious RM and move to new roles, and RPOs involved in repeated misconduct, to inform decisions on collaborations.
- RPOs and RIOs should establish clear protocols and mechanisms for cooperation in investigating and adjudicating cross-institutional and transnational RM cases, including cases where researchers from multiple RPOs and countries are involved due to shared research programmes and grants.

3. Pillar II: Research Culture Transformation

3.1. Fostering good research practices

Timescale: 2026 - 2030 Stakeholders involved: RPOs, RFOs and RIOs

OBJECTIVE	ACTION
<p>Risk identification & mitigation capacity</p> <p>Enhance the capacity of researchers to identify and mitigate risks associated with research practices</p>	<p>By 2028</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> RPOs — including institutional RECs — and RFOs should integrate a dedicated section into research applications requiring researchers to explicitly specify, consider, and evaluate risks and challenges to good research practice within each project’s specific context. This section should include an assessment of impacts and specific, actionable mitigation strategies. RPOs, RFOs and RIOs should provide guidance and support to researchers in developing effective mitigation strategies, ensuring they have the tools and knowledge needed to address ethical challenges proactively.
<p>Structured platforms for ethical discourse</p> <p>Establish structured platforms for ethical discourse and integrity discussions among researchers</p>	<p>By 2028</p> <p>RPOs should:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> organise institution-wide and department-led REI discussion forums, mentoring and peer dialogue programmes, and cross-disciplinary workshops to provide researchers with the support needed to navigate ethical dilemmas and foster a culture of integrity; and implement structured opportunities for researchers at all career stages to engage with ethical challenges through the establishment of RE/RI champions or representatives, who will serve as focal points for ongoing ethical discussion and collaboration.

Comprehensive strategies for good research practice

Develop comprehensive strategies for addressing ethical challenges and promoting good research practices

By 2030

- Institutional RECs and RIOs should be more comprehensively integrated into the broader scope of RE/RI activities to ensure researchers proactively address potential ethical issues across research projects.
- RECs, RFOs, RIOs and research institutions should work collaboratively to develop robust frameworks for promoting good research practices and navigating ethical challenges.

3.2. Supporting RE/RI for researchers across career stages

Timescale: 2028 - 2030 **Stakeholders involved:** RPOs, RE/RI bodies, RIOs and policymakers

OBJECTIVE	ACTION
<p>Leadership competency development</p> <p>Strengthen REI leadership competencies across all career stages</p>	<p>By 2030</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • RPOs and RE/RI bodies should implement structured leadership development programmes for mid-career and senior researchers, supporting them in gaining competency and skills in leadership and mentoring to inculcate a culture of integrity within the research teams they lead. BEYOND has created resources to support the training of research supervisors and mentors. • Competencies developed at senior levels should subsequently be embedded into training and development programmes for early-career researchers, ensuring the cultivation of the next generation of REI governance leaders.

Proactive institutional culture

Foster a proactive institutional culture that supports ethical research and reduces systemic pressures

By 2030

RPOs should:

- adopt a proactive approach to REI, investing in personnel, funding, and dedicated time for dialogue, reflexive practice, and collective learning; and
- encourage a research culture that embraces ‘slower science,’ reducing [performance pressures on senior researchers](#) and allowing senior researchers to mentor junior colleagues more effectively in research ethics and integrity.

3.3. Creating incentives for responsible research culture

Timescale: 2028 - 2030 **Stakeholders involved:** RPOs, RFOs, RE/RI bodies and RIOs, policymakers

OBJECTIVE	ACTION
<p>Revised incentive structures</p> <p>Strengthen REI leadership competencies across all career stages</p>	<p>By 2030</p> <p>RPOs should:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • move away from relying solely on traditional quantitative metrics — such as publication rates, journal impact factors, and citation scores — to evaluate researcher performance. Evaluations should also recognise research quality and researchers’ adherence to ethical research practices using multiple indicators in alignment with the Leiden Manifesto. • introduce incentives for compliance with Responsible Research and Innovation (RRI) principles, drawing on the CoARA Agreement on Reforming Research Assessment and the San Francisco Declaration on Research Assessment (DORA). • implement a more holistic approach to academic career progression that recognises mentoring roles and participation in committees that promote RRI as academically meritorious activities, on par with obtaining research funding, producing research outputs, supervision, and teaching.

Ethical metrics in rankings & assessment

Integrate ethical metrics and indicators into research assessment practices and university rankings

By 2030

RFOs, RE/RI bodies, and policymakers should:

- design and introduce metrics into university rankings and performance indicators that assess the quality and ethical standards adhered to during the research process. These metrics can incentivise RPOs to place strategic emphasis on responsible research culture alongside other priorities.
- recognise RPOs in institutional reports and rankings for their contributions to creating a responsible research culture, encouraging other institutions to follow suit.

3.4. Inculcating nudges to encourage behavioural change

Timescale: 2026 - 2030 **Stakeholders involved:** RPOs, RE/RI educators and researchers

OBJECTIVE	ACTION
<p>Reflective & value-driven daily practice</p> <p>Integrate reflective and value-driven activities into the daily research environment</p>	<p>By 2027</p> <p>RPOs and RE/RI educators should:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • acknowledge and reward individuals or groups who consistently demonstrate strong ethical practices, even in resource-limited settings. Small but visible forms of recognition such as institutional acknowledgements and awards for exemplary practice can act as effective nudges, encouraging peers to align with desirable behaviours. • implement more sustained interventions beyond one-off workshops to create regular opportunities for researchers to engage with their values, reflect on the consequences of misconduct, and share experiences that strengthen community norms.

By 2028

- RPOs should design and implement honour codes that emphasise the role of individual integrity, and articulate core values such as honesty, accountability and respect to foster self-regulation in upholding RE/RI standards. RPOs should implement structured campaigns that promote these mechanisms, and embed them within a wider programme of engagement – including regular discussions on ethics and integrity – to foster an environment in which researchers are motivated by shared values and mutual trust rather than external oversight alone.

Evidence-based behavioural nudges

Promote consistent ethical research practices through evidence-based behavioural nudges

By 2028

RPOs and RFOs should:

- implement a system of nudges within the research environment, based on evidence-based understanding of behavioural factors influencing ethical conduct. Examples include prompts for ethical reflection, default settings in ethics monitoring forms that encourage transparency, and simplified procedures that make responsible choices the easiest option.
- embed these nudges at critical stages like data analysis, authorship decisions, and manuscript submission to make ethical behaviour intuitive and visible.

Ethics & transparency

Ensure that nudging interventions are developed, implemented, and evaluated ethically and transparently

By 2030

RPOs should:

- establish a continuous evaluation framework for all nudging initiatives, using researcher feedback to refine interventions and ensure that they align with human rights principles – including freedom of choice, informed consent and beneficence – and remain impactful; and
- treat nudges as an integrated element within a broader continuous-learning strategy, alongside training, mentorship, best practices, and initiatives to promote institutional culture change.

4. Pillar III: Evolving RE/RI Education and Research

4.1. Improving RE/RI training design and delivery

Timescale: 2026 - 2030 Stakeholders involved: RE/RI educators, RPOs

OBJECTIVE	ACTION
<p>Scenario-based & practical learning</p> <p>Embed practical, scenario-based learning to strengthen the application of RE and RI in real-world contexts</p>	<p>By 2027</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> RE/RI educators should incorporate interactive, problem-based learning approaches such as ethical dilemmas, case studies and real-world applications that will prepare researchers to navigate complex ethical scenarios in their professional work. Available resources include: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> BEYOND case-based learning activity and case-study collection Collated RE/RI case study resources from other EU projects Erasmus University ethical dilemma game Path2INTEGRITY trainer handbooks and learning cards RPOs should ensure that whistleblowing content is embedded into RE/RI training programmes.
<p>Adaptive, inclusive & flexible training</p> <p>Develop adaptive, inclusive, and evaluated RE/RI training programmes that address diverse research settings and participant needs</p>	<p>By 2028</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> RE/RI educators should deploy adaptive tools such as self-reflection apps and ethical sensitivity measures to personalise learning experiences for diverse audiences. The BEYOND Trainer Guide provides guidance on designing and evaluating teaching activities for different target groups, including students, early-career researchers, experienced researchers and supervisors. <p>By 2030</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> RE/RI training materials should follow FAIR principles and offer flexible formats accessible to a diverse range of participants, locations and contexts – such as online modules and downloadable resources.

Sustained cross-sector collaboration

Foster long-term collaboration between RE/RI trainers, research organisations, and ethics education experts to sustain high-quality training

By 2030

- RE/RI trainers and training developers should engage in sustained collaboration with ethics education specialists, or develop expertise in this field themselves, to ensure that training materials remain up-to-date with best practices in ethics education, advances in research fields and technological developments.

4.2. Measuring the effectiveness of RE/RI training to support adaptation

Timescale: 2026 - 2030 **Stakeholders involved:** RE/RI educators and researchers, RPOs

OBJECTIVE	ACTION
<p>Comprehensive & continuous evaluation</p> <p>Establish comprehensive and continuous evaluation of research integrity training effectiveness</p>	<p>By 2027</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> RPOs should implement both quantitative and qualitative evaluation measures to assess training effectiveness comprehensively, integrating assessment tools and resources from the BEYOND Measurement Toolbox on The Embassy of Good Science platform. Programme and departmental leads should establish feedback loops to continually refine training content and delivery, drawing on input from participants, trainers, and other faculty and researchers within the institution. Where possible, RPOs should identify opportunities to automate aspects of evaluation to reduce the administrative burden and manage facilitator workload.
<p>Structured feedback & evaluation frameworks</p> <p>Enhance the relevance and quality of RI training through structured feedback and evaluation frameworks</p>	<p>By 2028</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> RPOs and RE/RI trainers should implement structured evaluation frameworks and learning taxonomies to assess progression from basic understanding to advanced analytical and ethical reasoning skills. These frameworks should support consistency and comparability in evaluation, while enabling targeted improvements to curriculum and delivery methods. The BEYOND Trainer Guide and Measurement Toolbox are resources that can support the development of such frameworks.

Openness & knowledge sharing

Promote a culture of openness and knowledge sharing across the research community

By 2030

- RPOs should conduct ongoing longitudinal evaluations to capture the sustained impact of RE/RI training on both individual researchers and institutional cultures. Outcomes should be shared within and beyond the organisation to foster openness, facilitate cross-institutional learning, and contribute to an integrated culture of research integrity at national and international levels.

4.3. Addressing research gaps in the causes, contributing factors and consequences of RM and CRPs

Timescale: 2028 - 2030 Stakeholders involved: RE/RI researchers, RPOs

OBJECTIVE	ACTION
<p>Expanding qualitative & quantitative RE/RI research</p> <p>Expand qualitative and quantitative research into RE/RI including psychological, social and economic factors</p>	<p>By 2028</p> <p>RE/RI researchers should:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • conduct in-depth qualitative inquiry into the factors shaping RE/RI attitudes and behaviours, including addressing the research gap identified in BEYOND on how mental health and researcher well-being intersect with ethical decision-making in research environments; and • investigate in a nuanced way the context-specific drivers of misconduct including factors that influence CRPs.
<p>Researching emerging challenges, including generative AI</p> <p>Allocate funding and research effort to study emerging challenges, especially the role of generative AI in RM</p>	<p>By 2028</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Policymakers should establish dedicated funding streams to support studies addressing the emergent challenges posed by generative AI and its potential to exacerbate RM and create new CRPs. • RE/RI researchers, RFOs and policymakers should work collaboratively to ensure these research initiatives are widely disseminated and inform interim updates to institutional policies and training programmes.

Theoretical frameworks & practical tools

Develop theoretical frameworks and practical tools to underpin evidence-based policy decisions in RE/RI

By 2030

- Policymakers and RFOs should prioritise investment in developing frameworks and tools, including new [psychometric instruments](#), for data-driven policy interventions that mitigate RM and advance research integrity.

5. Pillar IV: Enhancing Public Trust and Societal Impact

5.1. Fostering research transparency and trust in science and scholarship

Timescale: 2026 - 2030 **Stakeholders involved:** RPOs, RFOs RE/RI bodies and RIOs, policymakers, academic publishers, researchers, RE/RI educators

OBJECTIVE	ACTION
<p>Public trust through communication & participation</p> <p>Enhance public trust in science and scholarship through proactive communication, stakeholder engagement, and participatory policy design</p>	<p>By 2027</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • RE/RI educators should address in researcher training the real-world consequences of eroding public trust in science and scholarship. They should highlight how distrust hinders knowledge generation, policy-making, and societal problem-solving, and how RM can be exploited by groups promoting scientifically disputed claims, populist movements, or authoritarian actors. <p>By 2028</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Multi-stakeholder advisory panels comprised of researchers, non-governmental organisations, community organisations, and policymakers should be established to review RE/RI policies and address emerging challenges. These groups can co-design trust-building strategies to strengthen public trust in science and scholarship. • RE/RI bodies should adopt a more participatory approach by involving the public – particularly those with an active stake in the research or who will be impacted by its results – in review and consultation processes to enhance transparency.

By 2030

- RPOs, RFOs, and researchers should implement anticipatory public communication strategies for politically sensitive research that pre-empt misinterpretation of results, engage directly with public concerns, and deliver scientific findings in a non-partisan and transparent manner.

Guidance & oversight for sensitive research

Allocate funding and research effort to study emerging challenges, especially the role of generative AI in RM

By 2027

- During prolonged investigations, or those attracting intensive public and media interest, RPOs, RFOs, RIOs, and RE/RI bodies should put interim measures in place to mitigate potential harm to researchers and scientific institutions. This includes designing and implementing communication strategies that maintain transparency and fairness while respecting confidentiality during investigations.

By 2028

- RPOs, RFOs, and national RE/RI bodies should issue guidelines for navigating politically sensitive research that emphasise scholarly rigour, transparency, and the importance of acknowledging potential biases. Researchers should be encouraged to integrate proactive assessment of RE/RI risks and accompanying mitigation strategies into risk management plans, particularly for politically charged studies.

Balancing confidentiality with public interest

Develop theoretical frameworks and practical tools to underpin evidence-based policy decisions in RE/RI

By 2030

- Policymakers should introduce legally robust regulations and oversight mechanisms covering both public and private research, ensuring adherence to RE/RI principles while balancing commercial confidentiality, public safety, and human rights. This includes creating clear mechanisms that balance the protection of commercial confidentiality and intellectual property rights with public interest requirements.

6. Conclusion

By 2030, reducing RM in Europe requires systemic reform grounded in fairness, inclusivity, transparency, accountability, and shared responsibility. RPOs, RFOs, publishers, policymakers, RIOs, RE/RI bodies, educators and researchers each hold distinct but interdependent responsibilities.

This Roadmap shifts the focus from reactive punishment to proactive culture-building. It positions RM cases as opportunities for institutional learning, aligns incentives with integrity, strengthens protections for vulnerable researchers, and recommends situation-based ethical training be implemented across academic fields and researcher career stages. Through coordinated action across governance, culture, trust-building, and research, the research ecosystem can move toward a resilient and trustworthy research integrity environment that sustains long-term public confidence in science and scholarship beyond 2030.

Annex A: Further Reading and Resource List

BEYOND Project Publications

Rodrigues, R., & Pizzolato, D. (2024). Insights on the socio-economic impacts of research misconduct. *Public Governance, Administration and Finances Law Review*, 9(2), 93–122. <https://doi.org/10.53116/pgafir.7721>

This article uses a socio-economic impact assessment methodology to identify and assess the impacts of RM and presents recommendations for policy and future research that take socio-economic impacts into account when addressing RM.

Slesinger, I., & Simm, K. (2024). The politicization of research ethics and integrity and its implications for research governance. *Journal of Academic Ethics*, 23(3), 759–765. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10805-024-09563-2>

The short piece examines the growing politicization of research ethics and integrity (REI), including online amplification, and offers practical recommendations institutions and researchers to mitigate its negative effects.

Löfström, E., Lindemann, T., Blom, F., et al. (2025). Fostering research integrity through training: The training materials of four EU-funded projects through the lens of pedagogical underpinnings and three taxonomies of learning. *Open Research Europe*, 5, 301. <https://doi.org/10.12688/openreseurope.20826.1>

Tammeleht, A., & Löfström, E. (2025). How do you know if research ethics and integrity training is effective? An overview of prior literature. *Ethics & Behavior*, 1–14. <https://doi.org/10.1080/10508422.2025.2493055>

Tammeleht, A., & Löfström, E. (2025). Measuring ethics training effectiveness: Introducing a toolbox. *International Journal of Ethics Education*, 10(2), 265–300. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s40889-025-00214-7>

These three articles examine how research ethics and integrity training can be designed and evaluated to ensure such training is effective, and propose practical tools for measuring and analysing training effectiveness.

van den Hooff, S., & Mežinska, S. (2025). The role of senior researchers in promoting good science: Obstacles and enablers. *Open Research Europe*, 5, 21. <https://doi.org/10.12688/openreseurope.19140.2>

This short piece examines senior researchers' professional responsibilities in fostering ethical research practices within their teams, and explores the challenges they face in fulfilling these responsibilities. It highlights how a 'slow science' approach and targeted training to promote better supervision practices can improve RE/RI culture.

Selected BEYOND Project Deliverables

Slesinger, I., Dilger, J., Kumar, R., Vinders, J., Rodrigues, R., Simm, K., Zameska, J., Lang, H., van den Hooff, S., Fanelli, D., Coman, A., Husum, T. L., Tammeleht, A., Löfström, E., Mežinska, S., & Lasmane, E. (2024). Insights from the literature review on behavioural ethics, moral psychology & case-based methodologies and review of real-life case studies of research misconduct. Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.13861343>

This deliverable provides an overview of the RE/RI landscape as a basis for BEYOND's work, including a scoping review of the literature and a qualitative analysis of real-life cases.

Holm, S. (2024). Systematic review of validated instruments for measuring research misconduct and questionable research practices. Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.12744109>

This systematic review identifies and assesses the quality of validated instruments used in the literature to measure aspects of RM and/or CRPs and provides recommendations for improving their quality and effectiveness.

Mežinska, S., Lasmane, E., Poļaka, I., & van den Hooff, S. (2024). D2.2. Report on the results of the BEYOND public consultation. Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.13906446>

This deliverable provides the results of a public consultation exercise carried out by BEYOND with researchers, students, civil society actors, industry representatives and the general public, and identifies key themes and issues identified from the analysed data.

Fanelli, D., Voodla, A., Uusberg, A., Andres, S., Iordanou, K., & de Vos, M. (2024). Report on contextually sensitive framework for defining QRPs. Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17941451>

This deliverable reports the findings of three studies on how CRPs can be more clearly defined, contextualised and assessed.

Uusberg, A., de Vos, M., Andres, S., Voodla, A., Fanelli, D., & Iordanou, K. (2025). Behavioral insights for improving research integrity. Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17871646>

This deliverable explores improving research integrity culture through behaviour change by means of a four-fold strategy of shaping competencies, incentives, communities, and opportunities to address undesirable research behaviours.

Bernabe, R., Löfström, E., Tammeleht, A., Slesinger, I., Sairio, A., Aryal, P., Khayadi, C., Dash, K. C., Kaila, E., Coman, A., Mbanya, V., Iordanou, K., Simm, K., & Husum, T. L. (2025). BEYOND guidelines for preventing and addressing research misconduct. Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17720039>

The BEYOND Guidelines provide structured recommendations for addressing and preventing RM using an ecosystem approach that recognizes systemic and cultural factors that influence research culture and behaviour, as well as the roles and responsibilities of multiple actors and stakeholders.

Sairio, A., Kaila, E., Videnoja, K., Löfström, E., Tammeleht, A., Simm, K., Iordanou, K., Coman, A., Husum, T. L., Slesinger, I., Bernabe, R., Mbanya, V., Aryal, P., & Dash, K. C. (Forthcoming). BEYOND best practices manual: a complement to the BEYOND guidelines for preventing and addressing research misconduct. To be available at: <https://beyondbadapples.eu/publications/>

The Best Practice Manual documents best practices and knowledge for stakeholders to implement effective and scalable interventions to improve RE/RI systems and better manage RM.

Rodrigues, R., & Pizzolato, D. (2023). Policy Brief 1: Addressing the socio-economic consequences of research misconduct. Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10776390>

This policy brief addresses the socio-economic impacts of RM and provides targeted recommendations for policy makers to reduce the frequency and severity of these impacts.

Löfström, E., Tammeleht, A., & Bernabe, R. (2025). The BEYOND policy recommendations on institutional research ethics and research integrity culture. Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.18111204>

This policy brief provides recommendations for policymakers, RPO leaders, regulatory agencies and RE/RI bodies on how to proactively foster a responsible research environment through strategic measures for reforming leadership approaches and organisational cultures.

Resource List

Web links

BEYOND project website: <https://beyondbadapples.eu>

BEYOND page on The Embassy of Good Science: <https://embassy.science/wiki/Initiative:667449ef-1c0a-4e06-8374-830c8ad68cb8>

BEYOND page on Zenodo: <https://zenodo.org/communities/beyondbadappleseu/records?q=&l=list&p=1&s=10&sort=newest>

ALLEA (European Federation of Academies of Sciences and Humanities): <https://allea.org>

CoARA (Coalition for Advancing Research Assessment): <https://www.coara.org>

ENRIO (European Network of Research Integrity Offices) website: <https://www.enrio.eu>

Embassy of Good Science platform: <https://embassy.science/>

ENERI (European Network for Research Ethics and Integrity): <https://eneri.eu>

Research Governance

ALLEA. (2023). The European Code of Conduct for Research Integrity: Revised edition 2023. <https://doi.org/10.26356/ECOC>

Coalition for Advancing Research Assessment. (2022). Agreement on Reforming Research Assessment. <https://zenodo.org/records/13480728>

European Commission. (2025). Living guidelines on the responsible use of generative AI in research

(2nd ed.). Publications Office of the European Union. https://research-and-innovation.ec.europa.eu/document/download/2b6cf7e5-36ac-41cb-aab5-0d32050143dc_en?filename=ec_rtd_ai_guidelines.pdf

European Network of Research Integrity Offices (ENRIO). (2023). ENRIO Handbook on Whistleblower Protection in Research. Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8192478>

International Organization for Standardization. (2021). ISO 37002:2021: Whistleblowing management systems – Guidelines. <https://www.iso.org/standard/65035.html>

Leiden Manifesto for Research Metrics. (2015). <https://www.leidenmanifesto.org>

San Francisco Declaration on Research Assessment. (2012). <https://sfedora.org/read/>

Slesinger, I., & van den Hooff, S. (2024). Designing an interoperable framework for qualitatively rich case study reporting and monitoring. World Congress on Research Integrity (WCRI), Athens, Greece. Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.19066336>

RE/RI training and assessment

Löfström, E., & Tammeleht, A. Resources to support the training of research supervisors and mentors. Embassy of Good Science. <https://embassy.science/wiki/Instruction:97e76e2e-e21f-412e-84cb-7ad9f0904d0a>

Simm, K., Parder, M.-L., Lang, H. M., & Kaaya, E. BEYOND case-based learning activity and case-study collection. Embassy of Good Science. <https://>

embassy.science/wiki/Instruction:Acbe0102-8c73-43fb-9d99-269d1ec173f8#Familiarize_yourself_with_the_methodology_used_for_this_training_activity

Exploring Case Studies. **Embassy of Good Science.** <https://embassy.science/wiki/Instruction:8f5800b2-db1c-442f-b557-fef23fb1fcfc>

Ethical dilemma game. **Erasmus University Rotterdam.** <https://www.eur.nl/en/about-university/policy-and-regulations/integrity/research-integrity/dilemma-game>

Path2INTEGRITY trainer handbooks and learning cards. **Path2Integrity project.** <https://www.path2integrity.eu/ri-materials>

Lofstrom, E., & Tammeleht, A. (2024). BEYOND – Whistleblowing for ECRs. Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14161068>

Selecting Appropriate Material and Effectiveness Measurement Tools for your Target Audience. **Embassy of Good Science.** <https://embassy.science/wiki/Instruction:204c2375-0867-4302-845f-cdc99e3d38bc>

BEYOND Trainer Guide. **Embassy of Good Science.** <https://embassy.science/wiki/Guide:D857e22a-342c-48b7-a1d5-a096a2fa1ebd>

Annex B: Methodology for Obtaining Recommendations and Validation

The methodology for identifying, consolidating, and validating recommendations for the BEYOND 2030 Roadmap comprised a structured, multi-stage process designed to ensure accuracy, relevance, and alignment with the project's objectives.

A total of 107 recommendations were systematically extracted and collated from 12 public-facing project deliverables. These included key outputs from across the project lifecycle, capturing insights from research activities, training materials, and dissemination reports. To ensure breadth and representativeness, recommendations were drawn from diverse sources to reflect the multi-dimensional nature of the project.

Each recommendation was classified by relevant pillar, thematic focus, relevant stakeholders, and indicative timescale for implementation. This classification framework supports targeted policy planning by clarifying which actors and time horizons are implicated in each recommendation. Part of the framework was adapted from the thematic areas and stakeholder categories deployed in Deliverable 5.1 - BEYOND Guidelines for Preventing and Addressing Research Misconduct, ensuring consistency in conceptual approach and terminology across the project. Similar or overlapping recommendations were consolidated, and duplicates were removed to produce a refined list that could be easily navigated and adapted for the Roadmap.

The extracted recommendations were then cross-referenced against the project's primary outputs, including the BEYOND Measurement Toolkit, the case-based training materials developed for the Embassy of Good Science platform, the BEYOND trainer guide, and six peer-reviewed project publications. This step ensured that the recommendations integrate project results and outputs to support the Roadmap's actions to achieve impact.

The refined Roadmap draft was submitted to the BEYOND Stakeholder Advisory Board (SAB) for validation. Feedback was systematically gathered and collated from SAB members, focusing on several key dimensions including:

- Accuracy and clarity of the recommendations
- Identification of content gaps
- Opportunities to link to existing work and external resources
- Quality of the document's design and presentation

The SAB's feedback was then integrated into the Roadmap, ensuring that the final set of recommendations is both relevant and endorsed by domain experts. Significant revisions were made to the content and format to align actions with objectives, define where additional evaluation measures are required to assess progress, and improve accessibility for non-experts. This iterative validation process strengthened the credibility of the Roadmap and aligned the recommendations with the needs and expectations of the intended user community.

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